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O'ZBEK TILI NUTQIY IFODALILIK VOSITALARINING LINGVISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada o'zbek tilida nutq ifodalash vositalarining qo'llanilishi haqida so'z boradi. Og'zaki ekspressivlik vositalari nafaqat tasvirlangan ko'plab rasm va hodisalarni oydinlashtirishga, kengroq va chuqurroq ochib berishga xizmat qiladi, balki ijodiy fikrlash darajasining ko'rsatkichidir; nutqning tasviriy va aniqligiga erishishda ulardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Maqolada, shuningdek, bir tomondan, his-tuyg'ular va his-tuyg'ularni ifodalash, ikkinchi tomondan, idrok bilan bog'liq bo'lgan bir nechta psixologik qonunlar guruhlariga asoslangan ekspressivlikning qisqacha tavsifi berilgan. Yo'llar va raqamlar aloqaning turli sohalarida teng bo'lmagan funktsional faollikka ega. Ular asosan badiiy adabiyot va jurnalistikada qo'llaniladi. Talabalarning ushbu vositalarni o'rganish bo'yicha olib borayotgan ishlari o'zbek tilini davlat tili sifatida o'rganish bo'yicha bilim va ko'nikmalarini mustahkamlashga yordam beradi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR nutq ifoda vositalari, troplar, figuralar, ifodalilik, og'zaki figuralar

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СРЕДСТВ РЕЧЕВОЙ ВЫРАЗИТЕЛЬНОСТИ УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье рассматривается использование средств выразительности речи в узбекском языке. Средства словесной выразительности служат не только уточнению, более широкому и глубокому раскрытию многих изображаемых картин и явлений, но и являются показателем уровня творческого мышления; их использование важно для достижения образности и точности речи. В статье также дается краткая характеристика экспрессивности, в основе которой лежит несколько групп психологических законов, касающихся, с одной стороны,

выражения эмоций и чувств, а с другой - восприятия. Пути и фигуры обладают неодинаковой функциональной активностью в разных сферах общения. В основном они используются в художественной литературе и журналистике. Работа студентов по изучению этих средств поможет им закрепить свои знания и навыки в изучении узбекского языка как государственного.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: средства речевой выразительности, тропы, фигуры, выразительность, словесные фигуры

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF THE MEANS OF SPEECH EXPRESSIVENESS OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

ABSTRACT: This article discusses the use of means of speech expressiveness in the Uzbek language. Means of verbal expressiveness serve not only to clarify, wider and deeper disclosure of many of the depicted pictures and phenomena, but are also an indicator of the level of creative thinking; their use is important in achieving imagery and accuracy of speech. The article also gives a brief description of expressiveness, which is based on several groups of psychological laws relating, on the one hand, to the expression of emotions and feelings, and on the other, to perception. Paths and figures have unequal functional activity in different areas of communication. They are mainly used in fiction and journalism. Students' work on studying these means will help them consolidate their knowledge and skills in studying Uzbek as the state language.

KEY WORDS: means of speech expression, tropes, figures, expressiveness, expressiveness, verbal figures

INTRODUCTION

Expressiveness is the most “situational” quality of speech, because, unlike other qualities, expressiveness depends on each parameter of the communication situation. Expressiveness has a “complex” relationship with other communicative qualities of speech. Expressiveness can be created by any language unit - from sound to syntactic structure. Ya.I. Retzker pointed out that any stylistic means are expressive, because have an emotional or evaluative effect. Often, even stylistically neutral language means can acquire

expressive meaning. “By analyzing the stylistic and expressive characteristics of individual links of the linguistic fabric and correlating them with the general ideological and artistic intent of the author, he establishes the expressive and stylistic tonality of the original” [86,78]. Literally, “expressiveness” is translated as “expressiveness” - this is a property of a certain set of linguistic units, ensuring their ability to convey the speaker’s subjective attitude to the content or addressee of speech, as well as the set of qualities of speech or text, organized on the basis of

such linguistic units. Thanks to this property of speech, we can “awaken” the logical, emotional and aesthetic areas of our consciousness.

RESULT AND ANALYSES

V.N. Yartseva gives the following definition of expressiveness: “a set of semantic and stylistic features of language units that ensure its ability to act in a communicative act as a means of subjective expression of the speaker’s attitude to the content or addressee of speech” [80, 591]. I.V. Arnold understands expressiveness as “a property of a text or part of a text that conveys meaning with increased intensity, expressing the internal state of the speaker and results in emotional or logical intensification, which may or may not be figurative” [10, 15].

The phenomenon of expressiveness is based on several groups of psychological laws relating, on the one hand, to the expression of emotions and feelings, and on the other, to perception (this includes, first of all, the opposition of figure and background as one of the main conditions of perception). The linguistic mechanism of expressiveness is the deviation from stereotypes in the use of linguistic units of various levels. The emergence of expressiveness as a characteristic of speech or text is influenced by the properties of the communicative situation: the intentions of the speaker/writer, the presumptions of the reader/listener, i.e. initial knowledge

and ideas with which he enters into communication [83, 43], as well as the linguistic and extralinguistic (social) context of the communicative act.

It is the situation of communication that dictates the choice of style and genre of utterance and serves as one of the distinguishing features of functional styles of language. Styles that are highly expressive include fiction, colloquial and journalistic styles. Styles with low expressiveness include scientific and formal business styles. Thanks to the use of speech expressiveness, any speech acquires expressiveness. “Expressiveness – the expressiveness of a text is the emotional state of the speaker expressed by linguistic and speech means, his subjective attitude towards the designated objects and phenomena of reality” [39, 869].

Expressive speech serves not only to express the emotions of the speaker, but also to influence the addressee. Emotional expressiveness and the emotional impact of speech are “not different phenomena isolated from each other, but only aspects of the whole” [69, 20]. As E.V. Dzhanzhakova notes, “expressiveness necessarily presupposes the possibility of influence, in other words, the emotional-expressive aspect of the utterance is focused on both the speaker and the listener, therefore attempts to contrast expressiveness as the ability of units to convey additional meaningful information and expressiveness as the ability of such

units “strengthen the author’s impact on the addressee” do not seem appropriate [49,112]. She also notes the existence of a number of figures and tropes specifically designed to influence the emotions of the addressee [49,113].

N.A. Lukyanova especially emphasizes techniques that serve to create units with an expressive internal form. She includes paths and figures among them. “An adequate analysis of the field of expressiveness is complicated by two circumstances. In linguistics, traditionally, there is no distinction between, on the one hand, lexical, phraseological and other means, in particular tropes, and, on the other hand, methods for creating such means” [83,44]. The lack of differentiation between two “aspects of the study of expressive vocabulary – linguistic (lexicological) and linguostylistic... leads to discrepancies in terminology: expressive units are called “words”, “units”, “means”, “techniques”, “figures” and “tropes” [39, 869].

Systemic-linguistic (or paradigmatic) means of expressiveness are found at all levels of language. Lexical carriers of expressiveness, along with various groups of expressive vocabulary, also include tropes. Some of the expressive lexemes have one-word neutral (not stylistically colored) correspondences, some correspond to neutral descriptive expressions of several words. At the lexical level, quantitative and qualitative expressiveness are distinguished. Syntactic

means of expressiveness include typified modifications of structural syntactic units that have expressive meaning.

METHODOLOGY

Skrebnev Yu.M. believes that repetition is a “syntactic figure.” Repetition can be sound, morphemic, lexical and syntactic [133, 591]. Verbal figures are unusual figures of speech that clearly express the emotional state of the speaker. For some subsystems of the national language, expressiveness as a speech strategy turns out to be system-forming. Expressive means of language are a traditional subject of rhetoric and stylistics; It is here that we find lists of “small strategies” of our speech – tropes and figures – varying in length and content [39, 31].

Researchers agree that the means of verbal imagery include, first of all, tropes: metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, personification, figurative comparison, epithet, hyperbole, etc., as well as syntactic-poetic figures: anaphora, epiphora, etc. Tropes - Lexico-semantic phenomena are different cases of using a word in a figurative meaning. However, as is known, not every figurative meaning for modern linguistic consciousness is figurative [70, 109].

Means of speech expression are stylistically colored units of language, such as figures of speech, tropes, as well as figures of rhetorical amplification of speech. Rhetorical strengthening of speech, for example, through the use of

figures and tropes, is one of the most important stylistic devices and at the same time a means of increasing the aesthetic level of the text.

Paths and figures have unequal functional activity in different areas of communication. They are mainly used in fiction and journalism. Tropes are less characteristic of scientific speech: in official business and scientific and technical texts these means are not used. Figures of speech are deviations from a neutral way of presentation for the purpose of emotional and aesthetic impact. A trope is any linguistic unit that has a displaced meaning, i.e. the background, shining through behind the literal meaning. The interaction and mutual enrichment of two meanings is a source of expressiveness. [39, 760].

In general, means of speech expressiveness are only stylistically colored units of language that are created and reproduced in speech by native speakers and which necessarily have their neutral analogues. Clarification of the issue of classification of means of speech expression is necessary to achieve feasibility in organizing methods of teaching Uzbek as a non-native language. In modern linguistics, the question of the classification of stylistic figures and tropes has not yet received unambiguous consideration, despite their long study. IN AND. Korolkov offers the following definition: "Trope (Greek tropos - turn, tropo - turn, deviate) in stylistics and poetics - an "unusual" (from

the point of view of ancient theorists) use of a word, in which the sound simultaneously realizes two meanings - allegorical (figurative) and literal (direct)" [70,109].

Rozhdestvensky N.S., who saw the purpose of tropes in the creation of "new names from the material of existing words in order to depict the subject of speech, to characterize it through a keyword," proposes to distinguish between six main tropes, noting, however, that "the classification of tropes can be only detailed according to various characteristics" [121, 51]. The issues of tropes and figures are also considered by neo-rhetoric, which is understood by modern researchers as a universal discipline located at the intersection of stylistics, poetics, pragmatics, semiotics and linguistic theory in communication. In neo-rhetorics, there are many attempts to clarify the meaning of both tropes in general and their specific types in accordance with modern linguistic-semiotic ideas. The main experience in this direction belongs to R.O. Jakobson, who distinguishes between two main types of trope: metaphor and metonymy, linking them with the two main axes of the structure of language - paradigmatic and syntagmatic [165, 10]. The final definition of a trope, formulated by neo-rhetoric, is as follows: "A trope is a semantic transposition from a sign in praesentia to a sign in absentia 1) based on perception, the connection between one or more semantic features of the signified;

2) marked by the semantic incompatibility of micro and macro contexts; 3) conditioned by a referential connection by similarity, or causality, or inclusion, or opposition" [98, 25].

However, all researchers agree on the basic assessment of the role of tropes: when a word is used in a figurative sense, its meaning is enriched and the image becomes more alive, which contributes to the general speech development of speech itself and the culture of speech. Shorter lists are contained, for example, in the rhetoric of E.N. Zarechnaya: epithet, metonymy, synecdoche, comparison, metaphor, personification (tropes); anaphora, epiphora, parallelism, gradation, antithesis, oxymoron, default (figures) [56, 29].

According to the correlation of tropes and figures with the qualities of speech by V.M. Moskvina gives the following picture.

1. To make speech diverse, such techniques as replacement with periphrasis, pronominal replacement, hyperonymization (replacement with a generic name), synonymous replacement, and other methods of avoiding tautology are used.

2. Euphemism techniques serve to fulfill the requirements of situational appropriateness of speech.

3. Diacopa belongs to the category of techniques of incorrect speech.

4. Figures of short speech are asyndeton, zeugma and other types of ellipsis, figures of deliberately lengthy speech are various types of amplification.

5. The figurativeness of speech lies in the latter's ability to "make the order visual, easily imaginable and unimaginable" in a way.

6. Terms and nomenclature names, as well as clarification figures, serve to fulfill the requirement of nominative accuracy.

7. The richness of speech is considered to be the speech of a person who not only knows the nominative, in particular, expressive means of language, but, above all, words and phrases with a figurative internal form, metaphorical and metonymic names, periphrases, etc. [89,143].

Many linguists divide figures of speech into two categories:

1) serving to fulfill certain requirements in speech (for example, techniques for avoiding tautological repetitions); 2) associated with deliberate non-compliance with such requirements. "If a deviation from the norm is not motivated, we have before us not a stylistic device, but a speech error" [7, 165]: for example, repetition figures are correlated with tautological repetitions on the basis of a motivated / unmotivated violation of the requirement for variety of speech.

Figures in both Uzbek and Russian linguistics include mainly syntactic means of expressiveness (rhetorical question,

rhetorical exclamation, rhetorical appeal, etc.). Analyzing the literature proposing the division of means of speech expression into figures of speech and tropes, we mainly focused on the classification of figures proposed by S.I. Vinogradov [73,160]. Figures of speech are “special figures of speech, fixed by stylistics, used to enhance the expressiveness of an utterance (for example, anaphora, epiphora, ellipse, antithesis, oxymoron, parcellation, parallelism, gradation, inversion, non-union, polyunion, chiasmus, silence and etc.)” [152, 109].

They are like expressive turns of speech, built on a deviation from the usual, natural speech standard and therefore receiving expressive meaning, based on a purposeful shift in meaning, on the rearrangement of speech elements and assume that the process of transferring meaning is in the process of implementation: the word has not yet lost its former meaning, and it gives the phrase a special semantic content [99, 132]. For example, “Sen etim emassan!” (G. Gulyam); “Men nechun sevaman Ozbekistonni?” (A. Oripov).

Research conducted in this direction shows that absolutely all expressive techniques and means, according to their purpose, are directly related to either the fulfillment or deliberate non-compliance with the specified requirements for speech, which makes it possible to classify such techniques and means according to their relationship with the quality of speech

(that is, systematization according to their purpose). The qualitative and quantitative selection of Uzbek tropes and figures when teaching Russian-speaking students Uzbek means of speech expression should be treated in the same way.

The means of speech expressiveness of the Uzbek language as stylistic means give elation and imagery to speech and thus significantly enrich the vocabulary of speakers of this language. They provide an excellent opportunity to avoid repetition, monotony, monotony, and stimulate listeners to philosophical conclusions. Means of verbal expression also have social significance in the sense that they help educate people, free them from vices and, by ridiculing them, contribute to the fight against them.

It is known that the Uzbek language, as one of the developed languages, is distinguished by the diversity and richness of linguistic units. Proof of this is also the means of verbal expressiveness (tropes and figures), which attract many researchers and methodologists due to their originality and multiplicity. As E. Begmatov notes «...тилинг бадий услуби бўёқдор восита ва имкониятларга бой. Улар тишуносликда тилинг тасвирий воситалари, шунингдек, троплар, услубий фигуралар деб юритилади» [20, 50].

So, for example, one of the leading specialists in the Uzbek language, R. Rasulov, calling them paraphrases, gives

the following characteristics: «...парафраза – предмет, воқеа ва ҳодисаларни ўз номи билан эмас, балки уларнинг характерли белги хусусиятларини тасвирий усул орқали ифодалаш жараёнидир» [117, 30]. Tropes are used figuratively in order to enhance expressiveness. For example, "Сув тиниқ бўлгани учун унинг ҳаракатлари аниқ кўринар эди. Тўғри бориб пўсти қолмаган, сув ялаб ўтаётган тол тўнкаси тагига қўл суқди. Амфибия одамдай сув остида ҳар замонда оёқларини силтаб, муаллақ ҳолда анча туриб қолди, кейин орқасига тисарилиб, сув бетига отилиб чиқди..." [22, 230].

Uzbek means of speech expression are formed on the basis of expanding the transfer of the basic meaning of the word. The use of words in a figurative meaning is the main indicator of vocabulary wealth and an important means of ensuring style and expressiveness of content and creating imagery. As the final result of the semantic transfer of a word in a language, metaphors, metonymies, synecdoche and other tropes arise. Transfer as a method of forming such expressions plays an important role. For example, "Ариқларнинг бўйларида, марзаларда кўклам нишонаси- ялпизлар бодроқ- бодроқ бўлиб уна бошлаган, бақаларнинг "вақ-вақ"и авжида. Чимзорлардаги кузда ўт кўйиб куйдирилган ажриқларнинг томирларидан чиққан янги, яшил барра гиёҳлар ер бағридаги ҳаётнинг қайтадан

жонланганидан далолат берарди. Сўппайган қовжироқ қамишлар изғиринли баҳор шамолида бир-бирига урилиб нохуш овоз таратарди. Икки лаби кўкариб қолган Димариқ ҳали ҳеч ким ва ҳеч нима лойқалатиб улгурмагани учун тип-тиниқ, билинар-билиномас, майин чайқалиб ётарди. [22, 227].

The means of verbal expressiveness of the Uzbek language usually serve figurative thinking, which, preceding the mythological way of human thinking, later contributed to the emergence of fiction. It is the means of verbal expressiveness in fiction, as A.D. Boboniyazov argues, that help to more fully reveal the beauty of the language of a work of art, and therefore the language itself to which they belong: « ... бадий асар тилининг жозибаси, унда қаламга олинган бадий тасвирий воситалар орқали очиб берилади» [29, 81].

CONCLUSION

Means of speech expression have now played an important role in the formation of the artistic style of speech as one of the varieties of book (functional) style. They are also used in modern Uzbek in other styles of the language, including colloquial. In the study of means of speech expressiveness, especially the tropes of the Uzbek language, moments of coincidences or discrepancies of linguistic phenomena in a bilingual system play an important role as an opportunity, on the basis of commonality and differences, to provide a lexical-stylistic comment that promotes

conscious understanding and use in speech.

It is also necessary to take into account the structural and semantic differences in the means of speech expressiveness of the Uzbek and Russian languages. From this we can conclude how important the comparative study of Uzbek words is in semantic-structural terms. Thus, when teaching expressive means of speech of the Uzbek language to Russian-speaking students, taking into account their linguistic features, which were mentioned above, is desirable. From the above it follows that without the means of verbal expressiveness it is impossible to imagine any language, including Uzbek, and therefore the process of studying it not only as a native language, but also as a non-native and state one. The study of the Uzbek language by non-Uzbeks pursues the goal of teaching spoken Uzbek not only in an official setting, but also in an informal one. Such situations inevitably require the use of expressive means of language along with neutral vocabulary.

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